

The famous experiment of Isaac Newton at the modern level or analysis of the possibility of direct confirmation of the hypothesis of the discrete motion of physical bodies

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"It doesn't matter how great your theory is, no matter how smart you are. If it doesn't agree with experiment, it's wrong".

Richard Phillips Feynman, theoretical physicist

Abstract

This article aims not only at a technical description of a direct experiment to test my hypothesis, but also at the attraction of universal human resources: businessmen, scientists, research engineers, scientific laboratories, etc. to accomplish this task. In addition, modern scientific equipment allows this study to be carried out.

Introduction

The hypothesis of atomic (quantum) motion is a hypothesis about discrete motion of physical bodies [1]. It is very close to the views of Epicurus. The ancient Roman philosopher Alexander of Aphrodisia (2-3 century AD), a follower of Epicurus, wrote: "... a moving body moves throughout the space, consisting of indivisible parts, and on each of its indivisible parts there is no movement, but only the result of the movement"[2].

For indirect verification and proof of the hypothesis, I applied the "Principle of optimal motion" as a practical conclusion from my hypothesis [1]. However, this is not enough, since the experiments were carried out at home: there is no scientific peer review, and experimental errors are not taken into account. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a series of direct experiments to test the hypothesis in order to finally answer the question of the ancient Greek philosopher Zeno of Elea: the motion of physical bodies is "continuous" or "discrete" or, as I assume, both "continuous" and "discrete" with a predominance of "discrete"[1].

I planned a similar study using a Heidenhain LIP372 linear scale with a signal period of 4nm [1, Fig. 4]. However, the step of this linear scale (signal period) is several orders of magnitude larger than the maximum possible signal period for a quantum of the motion. But more on that later.

Discussion and future perspectives

The alleged direct experiment to confirm the hypothesis of the discrete motion of physical bodies is a modern analogy of the famous experiment with the cart of Isaac Newton (Fig.1).

In the second half of the 16th century, Isaac Newton discovered the three basic laws of classical mechanics, set forth in his monumental work "The Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy". The equipment of his second law cart experiment ($a = F/m$) was extremely simple: a drip cart, an inclined plane, a ruler, and a stopwatch.

One of the conclusions of this experiment is that the speed of the trolley continuously increases with time. But maybe Newton was wrong and the speed of the cart increases discretely in accordance with the question of the ancient Greek philosopher Zeno of Elea, the opinion of Epicurus and my hypothesis.

Let's try to repeat this experiment at the modern level on the basis of the Picoscale V2 interferometer of the German company SmarAct GmbH with changed parameters. Perhaps the level of technology for measuring motion parameters achieved by mankind will be sufficient to answer the question posed by Zeno of Elea.

The new experiment will include:

- 1 .Instead of a cart with a dropper - a polished ball rolling along an inclined spiral glass tube in vacuum and a Michelson interferometer built on a laser and a reference mirror. The interference signal contains information about the displacement of the ball surface relative to the reference mirror. It should be noted that even with a rough estimate, the beam of light from the laser moves faster than the ball rolling through the glass tube by eight orders of magnitude.
- 2 .Instead of a ruler - an interferometer controller with a sampling frequency **0.1THz** and **50 pm** resolution.
- 3 .Instead of a stopwatch - a clock generator with a pulse frequency of **1 THz**.

Undoubtedly, the reconstruction of the Picoscale V2 interferometer is a very complex research process and will require large financial investments. But believe me, it's worth it: a possible confirmation of the hypothesis of the discrete motion of physical bodies and possible applications of the hypothesis are two practical conclusions from the hypothesis. Moreover, the first conclusion: for each mass of a body moving under the action of a force, there is its own optimal acceleration - we can apply it today. And the second conclusion: the discreteness frequency of the motion of physical bodies is in the range of **500 GHz** - it has a promising application, since it requires the creation of a gravitational wave generator of the same frequency, which is the starting point for creating a gravitational engine.

I propose to conduct research in two directions: according to my hypothesis and according to Newton. Below I present the theoretical data of these two directions, taking into account the distance - **8.95m**, traveled by the ball before the manifestation of the hypothesis (see below Theoretical calculation of the movement of the ball according to the hypothesis).

Fig.1. Scheme of the proposed experiment for direct testing of the hypothesis.

a – pulses from a **1.0 THz** generator, **B** – controller and junction box of an interferometer built on the basis of **PicoscaleV2** (sampling frequency **0.1THz**), **b** – pulses from an interferometer (**step 50 pm**), **C** – computer, **D** – optical fiber, **d** – laser beam, **E** - sensor head, **e** - inductive sensor, fixing the distance of manifestation of the hypothesis **8.95 m**, **F** - is a metal ball **45 mm** in diameter with a mirror polished surface and a roughness of **<1 μm** (for example, the Chinese company Changzhou Huari Steel Ball Co., Ltd.), **k** - is the maximum displacement of the ball during the experiment (**0.5 mm**), **f** - is a glass spiral vacuum high-purity tube with an inner diameter of **50mm**, an angle of inclination of **three degrees** and a length of **~ 9.5m** (for example, the Chinese company Donghai County Chong Rui Quartz Technology Co., Ltd.), the design of the glass tube attachment is not shown, **L** - is the tube to the vacuum pump, **M** – removable stopper, **N** – cable to the inductive sensor switching circuit, **O** – cable to the electromagnet switching circuit, **P** – electromagnet for fixing the ball, **Q** – hermetic cover for removing the ball, **R** – hermetic cover for installing the ball, **S** – contact of the inductive sensor, **G** – readout generator **1.0 THz** (for example, Company Atseva LLC, USA).

The main principle of experimentation: if, after a distance of **8.95m**, traveled by the ball before the manifestation of the hypothesis, the neighboring results of counting impulses from the readout generator **G**, per one step (**50 pm**) of impulses **b** from the interferometer are equal, then the motion of the ball is discrete (atomic).

Theoretical calculation of the movement of the ball according to the hypothesis.

Fig.2. Graph of the motion of the ball after passing the distance to the manifestation of the hypothesis (**8.95m**), graph of the motion of the ball on the path **0.5 mm**.

A - is the expected graph of the ball movement after passing the distance to the manifestation of the hypothesis (**8.95m**), **F** - is a metal ball, **f** - is a high-purity glass spiral vacuum tube, **g** - is the free fall acceleration (**9.8m/s²**), **g₁** - is the ball acceleration, $\vartheta_1, \vartheta_2, \dots, \vartheta_n$ – sections of quantum of the motion, **T** – period of quantum of the motion [1], $S_{\vartheta 1}, S_{\vartheta 2}, \dots, S_{\vartheta n}$ – elementary paths of quantum of the motion [1], **0.5mm** - maximum displacement of the ball during the experiment.

The purpose of this theoretical calculation is: to determine the distance (path) of the ball to the manifestation of the hypothesis, the maximum speed of the ball at this moment for comparison with the speed of the target (ball) indicated in the characteristic of the Picoscale V2 interferometer (**2m/s**).

The formula for the path **S** of the passage of the ball before the manifestation of the hypothesis for the mass of the ball **m** with uniformly accelerated motion, taking into account the quantization of motion [1, formula (3)]:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{n}^2 / (2 \times \mathbf{g}_1 \times \mathbf{L}^2); \text{откуда } \mathbf{n} = \sqrt{(2 \times \mathbf{g}_1 \times \mathbf{L}^2 \times \mathbf{S})}; \quad (1)$$

where: **n** - is the number of quantum of motion of the ball before the manifestation of the hypothesis,

$$\mathbf{g}_1 = \mathbf{g} \times \sin 3^\circ = \mathbf{0.513m/s}^2 \text{ - ball acceleration,}$$

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{5.37} \times \mathbf{10}^{10} \text{ s/m - a quantity that claims to be a constant in my hypothesis}$$

[1, formula (6)].

The elementary path of quantum of the motion in section \mathfrak{E}_1 :

$$\mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1} = (\mathbf{1/L}) \times \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{T}; \quad (2)$$

where: **1/L** [m/s] – elementary velocity of quantum of the motion [1, formula (2)],

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{1/(g_1 \times L)} \text{ [s] - period of quantum of the motion [1, formula (2)].} \quad (3)$$

That is: $\mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1} = (\mathbf{1/L}) \times \mathbf{1/(g_1 \times L)} \times \sqrt{(2 \times \mathbf{g}_1 \times \mathbf{L}^2 \times \mathbf{S})}; \quad (4)$

To simplify equation (3), we square both sides:

$$\mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1} = \mathbf{1/L}^2 \times \mathbf{1/(g_1^2 \times L^2)} \times \mathbf{2 \times g_1 \times L^2 \times S}; \text{ where } \mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1} = \mathbf{1/L} \times \sqrt{(2 \times \mathbf{S/g_1})}. \quad (5)$$

Let's take $\mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1} = \mathbf{1.1pm} = \mathbf{1.1} \times \mathbf{10}^{-10} \text{ m}$ in order to maximally observe the **basic principle of experimentation** (see above).

To simplify equation (4), we square both sides:

$$\mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1}^2 = \mathbf{2 \times S/L^2 \times g_1}; \text{ where } \mathbf{S} = (\mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1}^2 \times \mathbf{L}^2 \times \mathbf{g_1})/2 = \mathbf{8.95 m}. \quad (6)$$

Let us determine the maximum speed of the target (ball) after passing the path **S** from formula (2):

$$(\mathbf{1/L}) \times \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{S}_{\mathfrak{E}_1}/\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{5.023 m/s}. \quad (7)$$

The result obtained is approximately 2.5 times greater than the maximum target velocity - **2m/s** in the characteristic of the Picoscale V2 interferometer, which will require additional research by SmarAct GmbH.

Theoretical study for a proposed experiment to directly test a hypothesis according to Newton.

Figure 3 shows a graph of the motion of the ball during its passage through the path of manifestation of the hypothesis **8.95m**, which consists of **24** sections with a step of **50pm** - an impulse from the interferometer.

Fig.3. Graph of the movement of the ball during its passage through the path of manifestation of the hypothesis according to Newton.
A - is the beginning of the graph, **B** - is the end of the graph.

The calculation of the time for the ball to pass each section (**50 pm**) in accordance with the schedule (Fig. 3) is calculated according to the classical formula: $t = \sqrt{(2 \times S/g)}$ taking into account the difference in time of the paths traveled before and after each section.

N	The time for the ball to pass each section (50 pm) in accordance with the schedule (Fig. 3) $\times 10^{-11}$ [s]	Converting the passage time of section (50 pm) to discrete signals [THz]
1	1.6500032750928	0.06060594030904
2	1.6500032750883	0.06060594030921
3	1.6500032750836	0.06060594030938
4	1.6500032750790	0.06060594030955
5	1.6500032750744	0.06060594030972
6	1.6500032750698	0.06060594030989
7	1.6500032750652	0.06060594031006
8	1.6500032750606	0.06060594031023
9	1.6500032750560	0.06060594031039
10	1.6500032750513	0.06060594031057
11	1.6500032750468	0.06060594031073
12	1.6500032750421	0.06060594031091
13	1.6500032750376	0.06060594031107
14	1.6500032750329	0.06060594031124
15	1.6500032750283	0.06060594031141
16	1.6500032750237	0.06060594031158
17	1.6500032750191	0.06060594031175
18	1.6500032750145	0.06060594031192
19	1.6500032750099	0.06060594031209
20	1.6500032750053	0.06060594031226
21	1.6500032750006	0.06060594031243
22	1.6500032749961	0.06060594031260
23	1.6500032749914	0.06060594031277
24	1.6500032749869	0.06060594031293

Table 1. The time for the ball to pass each section (50 pm) in accordance with the schedule (Fig. 3).

We increase the frequency of the readout generator **G** by **10 times** to increase the measurement accuracy, that is, the frequency of the readout generator should be **1THz**.

Table 1 shows that when the ball moves according to Newton, there are no equal neighboring results of counting pulses from the readout generator **G** per one step (**50 pm**) of pulses **b** from the interferometer.

Theoretical study for a proposed direct hypothesis testing experiment on my hypothesis of discrete motion of physical bodies.

Figure 4 shows a graph of the motion of the ball during its passage through the path of manifestation of the hypothesis **8.95m**, consisting of **25 sections** with a step of

50pm - an impulse from the interferometer and each section is a quantum of the motion in accordance with the hypothesis.

Fig.4. Graph of the movement of the ball during its passage through the path of manifestation of the hypothesis on the hypothesis of the discrete motion of physical bodies.

A - the curve of the ball motion during its passage of the path of the hypothesis manifestation, **B** - elementary paths quantum of the motion, **1** - the absence of equal neighboring sections at **50 pm** in quantum of the motion, **2** - the presence of equal neighboring sections at **50 pm** in quantum of the motion, **1 - 25** - quantum of the motion, **n₁ – n₂₅** is the serial number or the number quantum of the motion received for each quantum of the motion of the ball during its passage through the path of manifestation of the hypothesis.

It should be noted that **n₁** was calculated by formula (1), the remaining serial numbers quantum of the motion were obtained by adding 1. The elementary paths of quantum of the motion were obtained by formulas (2) and (3):

$$S_3 = n / (g1 \times L^2) \tag{8}$$

The calculation of the time for the ball to pass through the section (**50 pm**) for each quantum of the motion in accordance with the schedule (Fig. 4) is given by the formula:

$$t_n = (0.5 \times 10^{-10}) \times L/n \quad (9)$$

Formula (9) was obtained from formulas (3) and (8)

N	The time for the ball to pass through the sections (50 pm) for each quantum of the motion in accordance with the schedule (Fig. 4) $\times 10^{-11}$ [s]	Converting the passage time of sections (50 pm) for each quantum of the motion into discrete signals [THz]
1	1.6500032752629	0.06060594030280
2	1.6500032752528	0.06060594030317
3	1.6500032752427	0.06060594030354
4	1.6500032752326	0.06060594030391
5	1.6500032752224	0.06060594030428
6	1.6500032752122	0.06060594030466
7	1.6500032752021	0.06060594030503
8	1.6500032751920	0.06060594030540
9	1.6500032751819	0.06060594030577
10	1.6500032751717	0.06060594030615
11	1.6500032751615	0.06060594030652
12	1.6500032751514	0.06060594030689
13	1.6500032751413	0.06060594030726
14	1.6500032751311	0.06060594030764
15	1.6500032751210	0.06060594030801
16	1.6500032751109	0.06060594030838
17	1.6500032751007	0.06060594030875
18	1.6500032750906	0.06060594030912
19	1.6500032750804	0.06060594030950
20	1.6500032750703	0.06060594030987
21	1.6500032750602	0.06060594031024
22	1.6500032750500	0.06060594031062
23	1.6500032750399	0.06060594031099
24	1.6500032750297	0.06060594031136
25	1.6500032750196	0.06060594031173

Table 2. Time of passage of the sections by the ball (**50 pm**) for each quantum of the motion in accordance with the schedule (Fig.4).

We increase the frequency of the readout generator **G** by **10 times** to increase the measurement accuracy, that is, the frequency of the readout generator should be **~1THz**.

Figure 4 shows that when the ball moves according to the hypothesis, there are equal neighboring results of counting pulses from the readout generator **G**, per one step (**50 pm**) of pulses **b** from the interferometer after **3–4 quantum** of the motion, that is, a positive result of the experiment is possible.

Conclusion

It should be noted that the sampling frequency of the interferometer V2 is **10 MHz** and the sampling frequency of the interferometer controller in the experimental setup is **60 GHz**. This is about 1000 times more, so financial investments will be required to conduct the experiment, and therefore I repeat: this article aims to attract general human resources: businessmen, scientists - physicists, research engineers, scientific laboratories, etc. to accomplish this task.

References

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- [3] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=91J0WNhHN-c>